

High performance Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers using catalyst-coated membranes with exceptionally redox-active Ni-O ligands

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Abstract

Anion exchange membrane water electrolysis (AEMWE) has the potential to combine performance upsides of Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis (PEMWE) with cost upsides of liquid Alkaline Water Electrolysis (AWE). However, practical AEMWE cell performances reported to date have largely failed to manifest these benefits, significantly trailing PEMWE cells. To fill those gaps, it is desired to develop new catalysts and membrane-electrode assemblies with substantially improved performance and durability.

In this work, we introduce Ir-free and F-free AEMWE cells and catalyst-coated anion exchange membranes (CCMs) with polarization characteristics and hydrogen productivities that closely match those of current state-of-the-art acidic PEMWE cells. These cells deliver an unprecedented current density of $>5 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$ below 2.2 V uncorrected cell voltage. High performing CCMs were prepared via scalable bar-coating process involving protection films. An *operando* spectroscopic examination of the CCM anode uncovered a surprising correlation between the redox active Ni^{4+} centers and their redox-active O ligands that have a O K-edge feature at approximately 529 eV. DFT calculations revealed that, contrary to prevailing views derived from iridium oxides, the distinct O K-edge feature is largely attributed to the $\mu_3\text{-O}$ ligands of the active bulk phases, rather than the $\mu_2\text{-O}$ or $\mu_1\text{-O}$ ligands at active sites. We conclude that this spectral feature is a sensitive indicator for the evolution of catalytic $\gamma\text{-LDH}$ phase for the present family of AEMWE layered double hydroxide (LDH) catalysts. It is necessary, but not sufficient for the actual evolution of molecular oxygen.

This computational-experimental study challenges the previously assumed correlation between spectral features at 529 eV and OER performance in Ni-based LDH catalysts and provides insights from the molecular to the technological level demonstrating how the abundance of redox active Ni-O species, *i.e.* high conversion ratio from as prepared $\alpha\text{-LDH}$ phase to the catalytically active $\gamma\text{-LDH}$ phase, in NiX -based AEMWE anodes ($X = \text{Fe, Co, Mn}$) together with innovative CCM preparation boosts their AEMWE cell performance to values rivaling state-of-the-art PEMWE cell technology.

Green hydrogen produced via water electrolysis powered by renewable energy is attracting much attention in the transformation process of our energy and industry systems. Today, three different major types of low-temperature water electrolyzers at varying technology maturity levels exist: proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE), liquid alkaline water electrolysis (AWE) and anion exchange membrane water electrolysis (AEMWE). PEMWE is an early market energy technology for supplying green hydrogen. The main appeal of PEMWE cells and stacks arises from their high current densities $>5 \text{ Acm}^{-2}$ at cell voltages below 2 V in research cells, in part thanks to low membrane resistance. This is conducive to reduced stack sizes and low capital expenditures. Also, PEMWE is the most load-flexible one of the three technologies. However, PEMWE requires the deployment of scarce noble metal catalysts, perfluorinated membranes and ionomers, and noble metal-coated stack components to sustain the highly acidic environment.¹⁻³ This may cause high and possibly unpredictable material cost and supply limitations at larger scales.⁴⁻⁶ AWE cells allow the use of low-cost component materials, an advantage that is offset by limited current and power densities, the corrosive electrolyte coupled to reduced load flexibility. As a result, large stack sizes are required for AWE causing long start-up and shut-down times, limiting integration with fluctuating renewable energy.

AEMWE combines advantages of both PEMWE and AWE: small stack sizes capable of fast start-up and shut-down and thus compatible with fluctuating renewable energy coupled with low-cost catalysts, stack hardware and fluorine-free membranes.^{1-3,7} Thus, it constitutes a promising and reasonable option for large-scale sustainable production of hydrogen. As a consequence, research on AEMWE increased significantly and fast over recent years.⁸ To date, a broad variety of highly conductive and stable anion exchange membranes (AEM) have emerged showing good performances in single cells.⁹⁻¹¹ While high current densities at the Ampere cm^{-2} level have been reported using high Ir-loaded AEMWE anodes (with Ir loadings of up to $0.5 \text{ mg}_{\text{Ir}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), this remains a grand challenge for Ir-free AEMWE cells, whose performances have been sharply falling short of state-of-art PEMWE cells.^{1,12-15} This is why the design and availability of high-performance, Ir-free, and stable AEMWE cells delivering $>5 \text{ Acm}^{-2}$ at cell potentials near 2 V has remained a major technology challenge. The present contribution will address and offer solutions to this challenge.

Herein, we report the design, assembly, and component analysis of Ir-free AEMWE cells that approach the current-potential characteristics as well as hydrogen productivity of state-of-art acidic PEMWE cells. The AEMWE cells reported herein deliver a previously unachieved current density of $>5 \text{ Acm}^{-2}$ near 2 V uncorrected cell voltage. At a current density of 4 Acm^{-2} , the described AEMWE cells trail today's PEMWE cells by a mere 150 mV in terms of IR-corrected kinetic cell voltage. This is testament to the outstanding catalytic reactivity of the electrodes, in particular the oxygen evolving anode. At a cell voltage of 1.8 V, corresponding to a cell efficiency, η , of 82%, the present AEMWE cell continues to yield $> 2 \text{ Acm}^{-2}$. This exceptional performance was made possible using a previously unavailable catalyst-coated anion exchange membrane (CCMs) preparation method,¹⁵ incorporating an Ir-free NiFe layered double hydroxide (LDH) anode formulation with exceptional redox electrochemistry. What sets the molecular characteristics of the present CCM anode apart from other Ni-based materials^{16,17} is the unusually high ratio of structural transformation of the semiconducting α -LDH phase into the conducting and catalytically active γ -LDH phase. A detailed spectroscopic analysis of the CCM anode revealed a previously elusive coupling of redox active Ni^{4+} centers and their O ligands by using *operando* synchrotron soft X-ray O K-edge and Ni L-edge spectroscopy. Our spectroscopic experiments are supported by previously unavailable DFT-based computational predictions of O K-edge spectra of all three LDH catalysts. In contrast to commonly held views derived from studies on iridium oxide, our computations relate the chemical and structural identity of the activated O ligands of the γ -LDH phase to a combination of μ_3 -O species at basal planes and catalytically active μ_1 -O and

μ_2 -O ligands at edge sites. As a result, for Ni-based LDH OER catalysts, we argue that a characteristic spectral O K-edge feature near 529 eV serves as an indicator for the presence of the catalytically active γ -LDH phase.

Results and Discussion

In the following sections we present the design of highly active and stable AEMWE cells, that were made possible by the combination of i) a novel coating strategy for (CCMs), ii) exceptionally active Ir-free Ni based anode electrocatalysts, and iii) state-of-art commercial alkaline exchange membranes (AEMs) and ionomers. As the fundamental catalytic materials characteristics of the used anode catalysts is pivotal to account for the resulting electrolyzer performance, we first present the fundamental catalytic properties of the anode catalysts in detail prior to discussing the technological CCM preparation and AEMWE cell performance.

Anode catalyst voltammetry. The anode of the AEMWE CCM consisted of a powder thin-film of a solvothermally prepared NiFe layered double hydroxide. The favorable ohmic-drop (iR)-corrected kinetic cell voltages of the AEMWE cells, discussed further below, originated from the geometric and electronic properties of the NiFe LDH anode catalysts. To learn more about the molecular properties of the NiFe LDH material, we characterized it in comparison to NiCo LDH and NiMn LDH reference catalysts. Comparative electrochemical geometric area-normalized catalytic OER activities at comparable catalyst loadings of NiFe, NiCo and NiMn LDHs were obtained from Rotating Disk Electrode (RDE) measurements in alkaline electrolytes of varying KOH concentrations (Fig. 1a, b). NiMn LDH was evidently the least active OER catalyst, followed in order by NiCo LDH and NiFe LDH. Interestingly, the characteristic Ni redox wave, indicating the onset of hole injection into the Ni-based catalyst, followed a different trend, namely NiCo < NiMn < NiFe LDH (Figure S1). Evidently, the detailed onset potential of the OER surface catalysis is not directly coupled to the emergence of higher Ni redox states. A comparison of our solvothermal layered NiFe LDH with commercial hydrous IrO_x and NiFeO_x OER electrocatalysts highlights the benefits of the Platinum Group Metal (PGM)-free NiFe LDH OER catalysts over conventional state-of-art anode catalysts (Fig. 1c). The electrochemical stability of the NiFe LDH during accelerated stress tests (ASTs, Table S2 and Figure S2 – 4) relative to commercial hydrous IrO_x and relative to NiCo and NiMn LDH was investigated and results are depicted in Fig. S3 and Fig. S4. Evidently NiFe LDH exhibited a favorable stability which qualifies it as the most suitable AEMWE anode catalyst. Finally, Fig. 1d reports the cyclic voltammetry and catalytic OER reactivity of NiFe LDH and IrO_x after the AST in 1 M KOH. While both materials suffered from performance decays, NiFe LDH outperformed commercial IrO_x. This is most likely due to irreversible redox processes of hydrous IrO_x in alkaline environments and the consequent formation of soluble Ir, which result in severe material loss.¹⁸⁻²⁰ By contrast, reversible geometric transformations between the catalytic inactive α -NiFe LDH phase and the catalytic active γ -NiFe LDH phase lead to improved tolerance against dissolution during ASTs.^{21,22} Even though the correlation of catalytic activity trends between RDE and Membrane Electrode Assembly (MEA) single cells has been reported challenging²³⁻²⁵ our data and cell building procedures evidence that the present NiFe LDH OER catalyst can be processed into stable and active CCMs that reveal previously unachieved AEMWE cell power densities.

Anode catalyst surface area and interfacial capacitance. To learn more about the origin of the observed voltammetric reactivity trends, we first investigated the trend in the real electrochemical surface area (ECSA) of the three LDH catalysts. As reliable sorption techniques to determine the ECSA of oxidic powder materials have remained elusive, researcher traditionally resort to proxy characteristics, such as the area-normalized interfacial capacitance, C_{dl} , of the catalyst powder films. Values for C_{dl} are accessible from the slope of capacitive current – potential scan rate relations taken

in non-faradaic potential windows. However, the non-conductive nature of Ni LDH catalyst films below the Ni redox waves precludes the use of voltammetry-derived C_{dl} values.²⁶ Instead, interfacial capacitance values, relevant and reliable as ECSA proxy values, are accessible using the experimentally accessible adsorbate capacitance (C_a) extracted from complex impedance measurements under catalytic OER operating potentials.^{21,27-29} Adsorbate capacitance, C_a , is believed to represent the differential pseudocapacitive charge injected into the surface by surface redox processes and their reactive intermediates at a given electrode potential. Supplemental discussion 2.1 provides the details of our C_a measurements using potentiostatic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (PEIS) and galvanostatic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (GEIS). Both methods resulted in very similar adsorbate capacitances for each of the three Ni LDH materials (Fig. 1e), excluding the surface area to be a controlling factor in the observed OER reactivity trends. Thus, there must be other material characteristics accountable for the sharp catalytic reactivity differences of NiMn, NiCo and NiFe LDH.

Fig. 1: OER reactivities of LDH and reference electrocatalysts (a) Three-electrode measurements investigating the electrochemical properties of NiM (M = Fe (black), Co (blue), Mn (red)) LDHs and commercial reference materials (IrO_x (magenta), NiFeO_x (grey)). Comparison of NiFe-, NiCo and NiMn LDH in 0.1 M KOH (a) and 1 M KOH (b). c) Performance of NiFe LDH (black) compared to commercial IrO_x (magenta) and commercial NiFeO_x (grey) in 0.1 M KOH. d) OER activity in 1 M KOH of NiFe LDH

(black) and IrO_x (magenta) in 1 M KOH after applying 2000 CVAs with potential hold of 10 s at 1.23 V vs RHE and 1.63 V vs RHE. e) Investigations of the capacitance of NiM ($M = \text{Fe}, \text{Co}, \text{Mn}$) LDHs applying GEIS. The measurements were conducted in N_2 saturated KOH solution at 1600 rpm and RT.

Tracking chemical states and redox behavior of Ni-O motifs under *operando* catalytic conditions. To learn more about the origin of the OER reactivity trends of the three Ni-based LDH catalysts, we tracked the chemical state dynamics of Ni and O atoms at selected constant applied electrode potentials and during voltammetric potential cycling. The formation of the catalytic active γ -LDH phase from the inactive α -LDH phase has previously been coupled to structural transformations involving interlayer anion ejection and cation injection linked to lattice contraction.²² However, unlike for IrO_x electrocatalysts,³⁰⁻³³ little is known about the chemical state dynamics of metal centers and ligands during the formation of the catalytic active γ -LDH phase.

Fig. 2a reports potentiostatic *operando* X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) spectra of the O K-edge at a non-catalytic potential (+1.15 V_{RHE}), where the α -LDH phase is prevalent, and under conditions where the catalytic active γ -LDH phase is formed (+1.45 V_{RHE}). While the spectra of NiFe, NiCo and NiMn LDH recorded at +1.15 V_{RHE} were almost identical, *i.e.* showing one distinct resonance at 531.3 eV related to lattice oxygen, the spectra recorded at +1.45 V_{RHE} differed significantly in their pre-edge region. Around 529 eV (528.7 eV, more precisely), the NiFe LDH catalysts have a much more intense spectral feature compared to NiCo and NiMn LDH. In the absence of a more detailed understanding of the chemical identity and geometric location of these O atoms, we refer to these O species henceforth as “O-529eV”. We further attribute the integral intensity of the 529 eV resonance to the fraction of the α -LDH phase that has transformed into the γ -LDH phase. We thereby refrain from the commonly held view that the O-529eV species represent catalytic active surface intermediates of the OER process. Intensely studied in hydrous Iridium oxides, this very O K pre-edge feature has been firmly assigned to electron-deficient catalytic active O species featuring localized hole states, formally referred to as O^{1-} .³⁰⁻³⁸ Likely by analogy, yet lacking computational analyses, the 529 eV spectral feature in Ni-based catalysts was associated with similar charge redistributions of reactive O intermediates.^{16,17,39,40} Based on our computational analyses below, we challenge these previously held views, at least for the present layered γ -NiFe LDH OER catalyst phases.

To correlate the onset of the O-529eV species with features in the potentiodynamic surface voltammetry, we tracked the intensity of the spectral resonance at 528.7 eV during potential cycling for all three LDH catalysts as shown in Fig. 2b. We further contrasted the intensity scans individually with their own derivative and their voltammetry in Fig. 2c and Figures S9a,c. Fig. 2b shows how each LDH catalyst exhibited its own distinct onset electrode potential of the O-529eV species associated with the formation of the γ -LDH phase, in the order NiCo (1.15 V_{RHE}) < NiMn (1.30 V_{RHE}) < NiFe (1.4 V_{RHE}). The γ -LDH phase onset potentials thereby match precisely the voltammetric metal redox waves, both in the anodic and cathodic scan direction, retracing the characteristic voltammetric metal redox hysteresis. These results confirm that the O-529eV species form concomitantly to Ni redox states >2 and disappear accordingly. We note that the onset potentials of O-529eV species also fully match those reported from *operando* X-ray diffraction studies of the atomic lattice structure of Ni-based LDH catalysts.²¹ We conclude that LDH lattice bulk geometry and the emergence of O-529eV species appear to be closely coupled.

To get more detailed insight into the Ni redox state(s) upon formation of O-529eV species, we tracked the XAS spectral intensity at 856.2 eV, associated with Ni^{4+} (see also Figure S10),¹⁶ during voltammetric cycling and correlated it to the spectral O K-edge 528.7 eV resonances for NiFe LDH (Fig. 2d), NiCo LDH

(Figure S9b) and NiMn LDH (Figure S9d). For all LDH catalysts, the 856.2 eV and 528.7 eV signatures track each other closely in both scan directions. This striking similarity in the potential hysteresis evidences a close coupling of the redox transition from Ni²⁺ to Ni³⁺/Ni⁴⁺ and the formation of O-529eV species that indicate the formation of the γ -LDH phase. To elucidate the structural transitions of electrocatalysts, various operando characterization methods can be employed, with operando X-ray scattering being one of the prominent techniques.⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ For more insight into the correlation of structural and electronic information please refer to Figure S 11 and the supplemental discussion 5.1. While an atomic proximity between Ni⁴⁺ centers and O-529eV species appears conceivable, a causation between the two processes remains unclear. The direct evidence for the immediate presence of Ni⁴⁺ in the γ -LDH phase is an important mark of distinction compared to previously investigated NiFeO_x OER catalysts, where the detection of Ni⁴⁺ has remained elusive. This underlines the exceptional redox activity of our wet-chemically synthesized layered NiFe LDH catalyst deployed in the AEMWE cells below.

To establish a link to the catalytic evolution of molecular O₂, we note that for NiFe LDH, the Ni²⁺ to Ni⁴⁺ transition occurs between 1.40 and 1.45 V_{RHE} and starts to disappear cathodic of 1.35 V_{RHE}. The actual onset potential of molecular oxygen evolution, judged from Differential Electrochemical Mass Spectrometry (DEMS)²², lies more anodic of 1.45 V_{RHE}. This is even more so for NiMn and NiCo LDH. Thus, we conclude that the Ni⁴⁺- O-529eV states evolve prior to the evolution of O₂. In other words, the presence of the γ -NiFe LDH phase is a necessary but not a sufficient condition for the evolution of molecular oxygen. We suspect that additional kinetic energy barriers need to be overcome before oxygen evolution sets in. The magnitude of the kinetic barriers as well as the elementary step associated with them can thereby vary among LDH catalysts with distinct trivalent metals. In fact, a previous comparative mechanistic analysis of NiFe, NiCo, and NiMn LDH revealed that the (thermodynamic) limiting potentials, *i.e.* the electrode potentials where the last of the four elementary reaction step becomes downhill, are 1.68 V, 1.88 V, and 1.94 V, respectively. These values are more anodic than the calculated and experimentally observed α to γ -LDH transformation potentials. Furthermore, the last elementary step to become downhill is *OH \rightarrow *O for NiFe LDH, while it is *OOH \rightarrow O₂ step for NiCo and NiMn.²¹

Computational structural and chemical identification of O-529eV ligands. To elucidate the chemical and geometric origin and identity of the O-529eV species in γ -LDH phases, we carried out DFT predictions of absorption spectra of Ni-based LDH catalysts. The atomic structures of the catalytic inactive α -NiFe LDH model with the formula Ni₆Fe₂(OH)₁₆·CO₃·4H₂O are shown in Fig. S 12a and that of the γ -NiFe LDH model with the formula Ni₆Fe₂O₁₆·2K·4H₂O in Fig. 3a and in Fig. S12b. In order to account for individual variations, we calculated the O K-edge absorption spectra for oxygen atoms in the top ten layers (see numbered atoms in Fig. S 12a, b and Fig. 3b). The computational spectra for the OH in α -NiFe LDH did not show resonances near 529 eV, which agrees with our experimental results. By contrast, as anticipated from the O K-edge XAS experiments, the OER active γ -NiFe LDH phase showed notable differences from the α -NiFe LDH phase in the pre-edge region.

While the spectra of surface OH (both 1-coordinated atop μ_1 -OH and 2-coordinated bridge μ_2 -OH) do not show significant features at 529 eV, the oxygen atoms in the subsequent eight layers (O3-O10) demonstrate pronounced absorption features at that energy. These oxygen atoms are associated with 3-coordinated terrace sites (μ_3 -O), which are present in the brucite-like planes of the OER active γ -NiFe LDH phase. Consequently, the oxygen ligands likely responsible for the 529 eV resonance appear to be the μ_3 -O motifs.

Fig. 3c illustrates the spectral changes in the O K-edge during the transformation from α - to γ -NiFe LDH by presenting different ratios of the average spectra of individual oxygen atoms in the α - and γ -NiFe LDH phase. (The respective computational spectra of NiCo and NiMn LDH are given in Fig. S 13.) The hybridization between the 3d orbital of the transition metal and the oxygen 2p orbital increased as the bond length shortened and coordination remained unchanged during the oxidation process of octahedral Ni^{2+} and Fe^{3+} in α -NiFe LDH to $\text{Ni}^{3+}/\text{Ni}^{4+}$ and Fe^{4+} in γ -NiFe LDH. It is apparent that the signal at 529 eV increased with increasing fraction of the γ -phase. Hence the protonated μ_3 -species in the bulk of the α -phase do not have a resonance at 529 eV, while the deprotonated μ_3 -species in the γ -phase do show a signal near 529 eV. These computational observations confirmed that the spectral resonance near 529 eV in LDH materials can be related to the transformation from α - to γ -NiFe LDH, representing the shift from the inactive to the catalytic active phase.

Fig. 2: Operando O K-edge XAS and following the dynamics of O-529eV. (a) Operando (pre) oxygen K-edge TFY absorption spectra of NiFe LDH (black), NiCo LDH (blue) and NiMn LDH (red) measured at 1.15 and 1.45 V vs RHE. (b) TFY intensity at 528.7 eV during a CV between 1.15 and 1.85 V vs RHE at 5 mV/s for NiFe LDH (black) and NiMn LDH (red) and between 0.95 and 1.85 V vs RHE for NiCo LDH (blue), respectively. (c) Comparison of the TFY intensity at the maximum intensity of the pre-edge feature (528.7 eV) as a function of the applied potential during CV, its first derivative and the corresponding CV for NiFe LDH. (d) Direct comparison of the TFY signal of the feature at 528.7 eV and the Ni^{4+} feature at 856.2 eV for NiFe LDH. The measurements were conducted in 0.1 M KOH at RT.

To track the spectral changes during OER, we simulated O K-edge spectra of various reaction intermediates situated at the bridge site of γ -NiFe (01-10) surface, as shown in Fig. 3d. During the OER process, when bridge-OH is oxidized to O, the intensity of the peak at 529 eV increased. This indicates a stronger covalent bonding between the metal and oxygen. Similarly, in the subsequent step when O^* is attacked by OH^- to form OOH^* , the intensity of the peak at 529 eV increased, as well. Thus, if either OOH formation or O_2 desorption is the rate-determining step, surface intermediates O^* or OOH^* would contribute to the peak at 529 eV in the O K-edge spectra.

Fig. 3: Computational O K-edges. a) Atom structure of γ -NiFe LDH. The oxygen atoms at different depths from the surface are represented by different colors. b) Computational O K-edge of an individual oxygen atoms at the top ten layers with two atoms at each layer. The curve colors are consistent with the atom colors in a). All curves are normalized by the maximal values in the whole range. c) Average O K-edge of all oxygen atoms at the hollow sites of α and γ phases, and the combination of various α/γ ratios of 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, and 0.9, respectively. All curves are normalized by the maximal values in energy range around 531 eV. d) Computational O K-edge of an individual oxygen atom at the bridge site in different OER intermediate OH^* , O^* , and OOH^* , and the combination of various OH^*/O^* and O^*/OOH^* ratios of 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, and 0.9, respectively. All curves are normalized by the maximal values near the main peak (around 540 eV, among these range, all curves are almost identical).

While the relative intensity of peaks at 529 eV with respect to the main peaks in Fig. 3d varies for different intermediates ($\mu_2\text{-OH/O/OOH}$), distinguishing them in experimental XAS spectra remains a challenging task. To contextualize these findings with the previously discussed experimental XAS spectra from Fig. 2, we propose that the main contribution of the spectral features near 529 eV derive from $\mu_3\text{-O}$ species located in the bulk of γ -NiFe LDH. On the other hand, $\mu_2\text{-O}$ and $\mu_2\text{-OOH}$, which are present at the catalyst edge surface, also contribute to the 529 eV peak, but to a minor extent due to the larger abundance of “bulk” $\mu_3\text{-O}$ species, compared to edge and defect $\mu_2\text{-O}$ and $\mu_2\text{-OOH}$ species. These results demonstrate that it is challenging to assign a numerical valence state to the oxygen species responsible for the resonance near 529 eV in catalytic active NiFe oxides. Contributions of distinct species are convoluted. In this context, we recall that while for OER active iridium oxides the spectral resonance near 529 eV has repeatedly associated with electrophilic $\text{O}^{\cdot-}$ species,³⁰⁻³⁵ this assignment is purely formal in character and unlikely to reflect the physical reality. Finally, comparative calculations of surface OH^* -saturated and surface $\text{O}^{\cdot-}$ -covered NiFe LDH surfaces (see Fig. S 14-15 and supplemental discussion 5.1) showed that electrophilic (electron-deficient) $\text{O}^{(\cdot-)}$ oxygen species indeed contribute to the peak at 529 eV in the O K-edge of NiFe LDH. However, this contribution is significant only at potentials above 2V. We conclude from our computational investigations of NiX (X=Fe, Mn, Co) LDH catalysts that the 529 eV feature in the O K-edge is associated with the activation of the NiX LDH catalyst phase to the OER-active and conductive γ -phase.

Preparation of NiFe LDH-coated alkaline exchange membranes. Our insight in the favorable extent of phase transformation of the α -LDH into the γ -LDH phase proved a practical selection criterion of a suitable anode electrocatalyst for deployment as a catalyst layer in technological MEAs. Catalyst layers with catalyst loadings of about 1 mg cm^{-2} represent a key component of CCMs of AEMWE cells. Since inactive α -NiFe LDH will not contribute to the electrolyzer performance due to the absence of catalytic active O ligands, promising catalyst candidates should show a high conversion to the γ -phase. The NiFe LDH catalyst presented in this work showed an exceptionally high redox activity of the Ni-O ligand, and thus was chosen as the anode catalyst material for the preparation of CCM for subsequent AEMWE single cell testing.

While PEMWE technology relies on a hot pressing-decal transfer of thick anode catalyst layers onto cation exchange membranes, the high glass transition temperature of AEMs prevents the use of this coating technique in the area of AEMWE. In addition, since direct catalyst coating onto AEMs has been challenged by membrane swelling and shrinking, which result in unstable catalyst layers, today's AEMWE cell assembly is largely relying on catalyst-coated substrate (CCSs) procedures.¹⁵ We report the preparation of directly catalyst-coated anion exchange membranes (CCMs) using a wet-film bar-coating technique. After direct application of the catalyst ink to the membrane, the coating was stabilized and protected using a combination of a PTFE inner foil and an adhesive outer foil. The adhesive foil allowed fixation of the half CCM for direct coating of the counter electrode. Details are provided in the supplemental information. This coating procedure enabled the previously elusive generation of stable and uniform powder catalyst layers on swelling anion exchange membranes. Catalyst loadings were controlled by a choice of the catalyst layer thickness.

AEMWE single cell measurements using NiFe LDH CCMs. AEMWE cell measurements were conducted using CCM-based MEA incorporating the NiFe LDH anode. The electrochemical hydrogen productivity (cell polarization curve), probed in terms of the measured cell potential as function of the applied current density, and the AEMWE cell stability, probed as variations in cell potential at a constant current density, were assessed in a two-electrode zero-gap configuration at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. S19). Figure 4a evidences significantly higher current densities at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ compared to $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. At $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a current of 2 A cm^{-2} was achieved at 1.9 V , while at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 2 A cm^{-2} was achieved below 1.8 V . A previously unachieved current density of 2.3 A cm^{-2} was obtained at a cell voltage of 1.8 V . Unlike reported AEMWE cell designs that experienced severe mass transport losses below 5 A cm^{-2} , our AEMWE cell design remained kinetically and ohmic loss controlled up to current densities above 5 A cm^{-2} . A current density of 5.5 A cm^{-2} was reached at around 2.2 V cell voltage. These polarization values were not dictated by limitations of the AEMWE cell but were related to hardware limitations of the current booster.

Importantly, when compared to state-of-art PEMWE polarization curves⁴⁵ the AEMWE cell design presented here featured comparable current densities but at fully Ir-free electrodes.⁴⁵ The iR-corrected polarization curves display a mere 150 mV kinetic voltage difference at 4 A cm^{-2} . This modest performance gap holds immense advantages considering the cost impact associated with Ir-loaded anodes.

The present AEMWE cells also exhibited decent performance stability for over 110 h at a constant electrochemical load of 1 A cm^{-2} . At $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ the observed cell potential increase amounted to $600 \text{ } \mu\text{V}$ and $613 \text{ } \mu\text{V}$ per hour, respectively (Figure 4b). The majority of potential increase occurred within the initial operating hours. Consequently, at this point, a current density of 1 A cm^{-2} can be safely sustained for at least 110 hours of operation below a cell voltage of 1.8 V .

Fig. 4: AEMWE single cell measurements using NiFe LDH CCMs. Measurements of CCM based AEMWE single cells with $1.14 \text{ mg NiFe LDH cm}^{-2}$ and $0.5 \text{ mg Pt cm}^{-2}$ in 1 M KOH . a) AEMWE single cell measurements at 60°C (black line), 80°C (blue line) and 80°C up to 5.5 A cm^{-2} (olive line) including *iR*-corrected values (dotted lines) and the respective HFR-values used for *iR*-correction. Shaded areas show 95% confidence intervals ($n=3$). b) Stability testing of the AEMWE cell at 60°C (black) and 80°C (blue) over 110 hrs. The asterisk at 53h marks the time point where the cell's temperature was altered to 70°C . The asterisk at 110h indicates the increase to 80°C again.

Conclusions

We have demonstrated Ir-free AEMWE cells with previously unavailable polarization characteristics and hydrogen productivities that closely approach those of today's state-of-art acidic PEMWE cells. The AEMWE cells delivered an unprecedented current density of $>5 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$ near 2 V uncorrected cell voltage. At a current density of 4 A cm^{-2} , the AEMWE cells lagged behind reported PEMWE cells by a mere 150 mV .⁴⁵

The AEMWE cell design with alkaline CCMs was made possible by a scalable bar-coating process involving the use of an adhesive foil to minimize membrane swelling during the coating of the second catalyst layer.¹⁵

Beyond CCM process innovations, we attribute the cell performance to the molecular characteristics of NiFe LDH catalysts, which were benchmarked against NiMn LDH and NiCo LDH catalysts. In a combined experimental and DFT-computational effort to understand the uniquely high catalytic reactivity of the NiFe LDH anode, we reached deeper chemical and structural insights of relevant redox active oxygen ligands. Contrary to commonly held views, the spectroscopically probed oxygen species associated with the XAS O K spectral feature near 529 eV under OER relevant potentials were largely μ_3 -O ligands in the bulk, rather than catalytically active μ_2 -O ligands on the surface. Hence, this spectral feature largely indicates the extent of formation of the catalytically active γ -LDH phase, rather than being a direct measure of coverage of catalytic active intermediates for the release of molecular oxygen, as reported in previous spectroscopic studies of IrO_x OER catalysts. We further uncovered the unexpected presence of Ni⁴⁺ at non-catalytic electrode potentials for all three examined LDH catalysts. The potential dependence of this feature correlates with the one at 529 eV, suggesting a strong coupling between the two and the formation of catalytically active γ -LDH phase.

Our findings imply that actual oxygen evolution isn't solely reliant on the appearance of the absorption feature at 529 eV and the presence of Ni⁴⁺, suggesting that additional kinetic barriers play a significant role.

Taken together, this contribution demonstrates that advanced Ir-free and F-free AEMWE cells are rivaling established state-of-art PEMWE cell technology, providing a promising path towards more cost-effective and scalable hydrogen production solutions. Moreover, the herein presented work highlights the correlation between electronic and structural characteristics in electrocatalysts, which can only be unraveled by combining operando experiments with theoretical calculations. Understanding of such correlations is crucial for advancing the development of efficient catalysts for water electrolysis.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Methods

Detailed description of the experimental and computational details can be found in the supplementary information.

References

- 1 Khataee, A., Shirole, A., Jannasch, P., Krüger, A. & Cornell, A. Anion exchange membrane water electrolysis using Aemion™ membranes and nickel electrodes. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* **10**, 16061-16070 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ta03291k>
- 2 Henkensmeier, D. *et al.* Overview: State-of-the Art Commercial Membranes for Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis. *Journal of Electrochemical Energy Conversion and Storage* **18** (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4047963>
- 3 Falcão, D. S. Green Hydrogen Production by Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis: Status and Future Perspectives. *Energies* **16** (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16020943>

- 4 Minke, C., Suermann, M., Bensmann, B. & Hanke-Rauschenbach, R. Is iridium demand a potential bottleneck in the realization of large-scale PEM water electrolysis? *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **46**, 23581-23590 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.04.174>
- 5 Setzler, B. P., Zhuang, Z., Wittkopf, J. A. & Yan, Y. Activity targets for nanostructured platinum-group-metal-free catalysts in hydroxide exchange membrane fuel cells. *Nat Nanotechnol* **11**, 1020-1025 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nnano.2016.265>
- 6 Kiemel, S. *et al.* Critical materials for water electrolyzers at the example of the energy transition in Germany. *International Journal of Energy Research* **45**, 9914-9935 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.6487>
- 7 Vincent, I. & Bessarabov, D. Low cost hydrogen production by anion exchange membrane electrolysis: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **81**, 1690-1704 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.258>
- 8 Du, N. *et al.* Anion-Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers. *Chem Rev* **122**, 11830-11895 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.1c00854>
- 9 Fortin, P. *et al.* High-performance alkaline water electrolysis using Aemion™ anion exchange membranes. *Journal of Power Sources* **451** (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2020.227814>
- 10 Koch, S. *et al.* The effect of ionomer content in catalyst layers in anion-exchange membrane water electrolyzers prepared with reinforced membranes (Aemion+™). *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* **9**, 15744-15754 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1ta01861b>
- 11 Motealleh, B. *et al.* Next-generation anion exchange membrane water electrolyzers operating for commercially relevant lifetimes. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **46**, 3379-3386 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.10.244>
- 12 Moreno-González, M. *et al.* One year operation of an anion exchange membrane water electrolyzer utilizing Aemion+® membrane: Minimal degradation, low H₂ crossover and high efficiency. *Journal of Power Sources Advances* **19** (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powera.2023.100109>
- 13 Chen, N. *et al.* High-performance anion exchange membrane water electrolyzers with a current density of 7.68 A cm⁻² and a durability of 1000 hours. *Energy & Environmental Science* **14**, 6338-6348 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1ee02642a>
- 14 Park, D. H. *et al.* Development of Ni-Ir Oxide Composites as Oxygen Catalysts for an Anion-Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzer. *Advanced Materials Interfaces* **9** (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202102063>
- 15 Koch, S. *et al.* Toward Scalable Production: Catalyst-Coated Membranes (CCMs) for Anion-Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis via Direct Bar Coating. *Advanced Sustainable Systems* **7** (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adsu.202200332>
- 16 Wartner, G. *et al.* Insights into the electronic structure of Fe-Ni thin-film catalysts during the oxygen evolution reaction using operando resonant photoelectron spectroscopy. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* **11**, 8066-8080 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ta08961k>
- 17 Drevon, D. *et al.* Uncovering The Role of Oxygen in Ni-Fe(O(x)H(y)) Electrocatalysts using In situ Soft X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy during the Oxygen Evolution Reaction. *Sci Rep* **9**, 1532 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-37307-x>
- 18 Lee, Y., Suntivich, J., May, K. J., Perry, E. E. & Shao-Horn, Y. Synthesis and Activities of Rutile IrO₂ and RuO₂ Nanoparticles for Oxygen Evolution in Acid and Alkaline Solutions. *J Phys Chem Lett* **3**, 399-404 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1021/jz2016507>
- 19 O'Meara, L. D. B. a. T. O. Oxygen Electrode Reaction Part 2. - Behaviour at Ruthenium Black Electrodes. *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1* **68**, 839-848 (1971).
- 20 Qi, J. *et al.* Understanding the stabilization effect of the hydrous IrO_x layer formed on the iridium oxide surface during the oxygen evolution reaction in acid. *Inorganic Chemistry Frontiers* **10**, 776-786 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2qi02214a>

- 21 Dionigi, F. *et al.* Intrinsic Electrocatalytic Activity for Oxygen Evolution of Crystalline 3d-Transition Metal Layered Double Hydroxides. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl* **60**, 14446-14457 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202100631>
- 22 Dionigi, F. *et al.* In-situ structure and catalytic mechanism of NiFe and CoFe layered double hydroxides during oxygen evolution. *Nat Commun* **11**, 2522 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-16237-1>
- 23 El-Sayed, H. A., Weiß, A., Olbrich, L. F., Putro, G. P. & Gasteiger, H. A. OER Catalyst Stability Investigation Using RDE Technique: A Stability Measure or an Artifact? *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* **166**, F458-F464 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0301908jes>
- 24 Fathi Tovini, M., Hartig-Weiß, A., Gasteiger, H. A. & El-Sayed, H. A. The Discrepancy in Oxygen Evolution Reaction Catalyst Lifetime Explained: RDE vs MEA - Dynamicity within the Catalyst Layer Matters. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* **168** (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1149/1945-7111/abdcc9>
- 25 Hartig-Weiss, A., Tovini, M. F., Gasteiger, H. A. & El-Sayed, H. A. OER Catalyst Durability Tests Using the Rotating Disk Electrode Technique: The Reason Why This Leads to Erroneous Conclusions. *ACS Applied Energy Materials* **3**, 10323-10327 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.0c01944>
- 26 Trotochaud, L., Young, S. L., Ranney, J. K. & Boettcher, S. W. Nickel-iron oxyhydroxide oxygen-evolution electrocatalysts: the role of intentional and incidental iron incorporation. *J Am Chem Soc* **136**, 6744-6753 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja502379c>
- 27 Jeon, S. S. *et al.* Active Surface Area and Intrinsic Catalytic Oxygen Evolution Reactivity of NiFe LDH at Reactive Electrode Potentials Using Capacitances. *ACS Catalysis* **13**, 1186-1196 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.2c04452>
- 28 Watzele, S. *et al.* Determination of Electroactive Surface Area of Ni-, Co-, Fe-, and Ir-Based Oxide Electrocatalysts. *ACS Catalysis* **9**, 9222-9230 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.9b02006>
- 29 Watzele, S. & Bandarenka, A. S. Quick Determination of Electroactive Surface Area of Some Oxide Electrode Materials. *Electroanalysis* **28**, 2394-2399 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1002/elan.201600178>
- 30 Pfeifer, V. *et al.* In situ observation of reactive oxygen species forming on oxygen-evolving iridium surfaces. *Chem Sci* **8**, 2143-2149 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6sc04622c>
- 31 Nong, H. N. *et al.* The Role of Surface Hydroxylation, Lattice Vacancies and Bond Covalency in the Electrochemical Oxidation of Water (OER) on Ni-Depleted Iridium Oxide Catalysts. *Zeitschrift für Physikalische Chemie* **234**, 787-812 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1515/zpch-2019-1460>
- 32 Nong, H. N. *et al.* Key role of chemistry versus bias in electrocatalytic oxygen evolution. *Nature* **587**, 408-413 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2908-2>
- 33 Frevel, L. J. *et al.* In Situ X-ray Spectroscopy of the Electrochemical Development of Iridium Nanoparticles in Confined Electrolyte. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **123**, 9146-9152 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.9b00731>
- 34 Pfeifer, V. *et al.* Reactive oxygen species in iridium-based OER catalysts. *Chem Sci* **7**, 6791-6795 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6sc01860b>
- 35 Pfeifer, V. *et al.* The electronic structure of iridium oxide electrodes active in water splitting. *Phys Chem Chem Phys* **18**, 2292-2296 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1039/c5cp06997a>
- 36 Massue, C. *et al.* Reactive Electrophilic O(I-) Species Evidenced in High-Performance Iridium Oxohydroxide Water Oxidation Electrocatalysts. *ChemSusChem* **10**, 4786-4798 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201701291>
- 37 Nong, H. N. *et al.* A unique oxygen ligand environment facilitates water oxidation in hole-doped IrNiOx core-shell electrocatalysts. *Nature Catalysis* **1**, 841-851 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41929-018-0153-y>
- 38 Reier, T. *et al.* Molecular Insight in Structure and Activity of Highly Efficient, Low-Ir Ir-Ni Oxide Catalysts for Electrochemical Water Splitting (OER). *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **137**, 13031-13040 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.5b07788>

- 39 Suntivich, J. *et al.* Estimating Hybridization of Transition Metal and Oxygen States in Perovskites from O K-edge X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **118**, 1856-1863 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp410644j>
- 40 Lafuerza, S. *et al.* Origin of the pre-peak features in the oxygen K-edge x-ray absorption spectra of LaFeO(3) and LaMnO(3) studied by Ga substitution of the transition metal ion. *J Phys Condens Matter* **23**, 325601 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/23/32/325601>
- 41 Magnussen, O. M. *et al.* In Situ and Operando X-ray Scattering Methods in Electrochemistry and Electrocatalysis. *Chemical Reviews* **124**, 629-721 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.3c00331>
- 42 Chatenet, M. *et al.* Water electrolysis: from textbook knowledge to the latest scientific strategies and industrial developments. *Chemical Society Reviews* **51**, 4583-4762 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0CS01079K>
- 43 Ding, H., Liu, H., Chu, W., Wu, C. & Xie, Y. Structural Transformation of Heterogeneous Materials for Electrocatalytic Oxygen Evolution Reaction. *Chemical Reviews* **121**, 13174-13212 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.1c00234>
- 44 van Oversteeg, C. H. M., Doan, H. Q., de Groot, F. M. F. & Cuk, T. In situ X-ray absorption spectroscopy of transition metal based water oxidation catalysts. *Chemical Society Reviews* **46**, 102-125 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6CS00230G>
- 45 Bernt, M., Siebel, A. & Gasteiger, H. A. Analysis of Voltage Losses in PEM Water Electrolyzers with Low Platinum Group Metal Loadings. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* **165**, F305-F314 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0641805jes>

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Author contributions

M.K., H.T., F.D. and P.S. conceived and designed the experiments. M.K. and F.L. synthesized the NiX LDHs and performed the electrochemistry experiments. P.W.B. assisted in the electrochemistry experiments. H.T. performed the *operando* X-ray absorption spectroscopy measurements and analyzed the data. A.W. assisted in the *operando* spectroscopy measurements. S.K., M.E. and L.M. fabricated and assembled the single cells and conducted the AEMWE single cell measurements. J.Z. performed the DFT calculations and analysis with support from Z.Z.. M.K., H.T., J.Z., Z.Z., F.D. and P.S. wrote and revised the manuscript. G.S., S.V., A.K., M.K. and P.S. contributed to funding acquisition, project administration and supervision. All of the authors discussed the results and commented on the manuscript.

Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

Supplementary information is available for this paper at <https://...>

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